

Field-induced alignment dynamics in suspensions of polarizable rods

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Fluids composed of polarizable particles exhibit tunable structural and functional properties when subjected to external electric fields, as the particles tend to reorient and align along the field direction. This field-induced anisotropy leads to pronounced changes in macroscopic properties, rendering these systems highly relevant for applications in nanotechnology. Understanding the dynamics of their response to external fields is crucial for designing responsive materials with fast and controllable actuation. In this work, we employ molecular simulation to study the behavior of suspensions of polarizable rod-like particles under the action of a uniform electric field, with particular attention to the transient dynamics associated with the switching on and off of the field. Induced dipoles are modeled by independently varying charge magnitude and field strength, yielding a variable effective polarizability. The system is studied in a dense regime, where interparticle interactions play a significant role and are implicitly controlled *via* pressure. We investigate how the characteristic response time depends on the competition between thermal motion and electric forces across a range of temperatures and field strengths. Our results reveal a rich dynamical behavior: at low to moderate field intensities, increasing the temperature significantly reduces the response time, as thermal agitation facilitates reorientation. However, beyond a critical field strength, the response time plateaus, becoming effectively temperature-independent. This saturation indicates a regime where the aligning torque from the field dominates over thermal fluctuations, setting a lower bound for how fast the system can respond. These findings provide quantitative insights into the tunability and limitations of field-responsive materials, offering valuable guidance for optimizing their performance in practical applications requiring fast switching, stability, or temperature robustness.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, nanomaterials capable of adapting their physical properties in response to external stimuli—commonly known as stimuli-responsive or *smart* nanomaterials—have attracted considerable attention. These materials exhibit reversible and controllable changes when exposed to external factors such as temperature, mechanical stress, light, or electric and magnetic fields. Among them, particularly well-studied systems are composed of either soft or rigid nanoparticles (NPs), each exhibiting distinct response mechanisms. Soft, deformable particles like microgels undergo complex swelling and structural transitions governed by the interplay between elastic and osmotic forces [1]. Rigid non-deformable NPs can be responsive, for instance by adapting to external fields through induced polarization, as seen in electrorheological fluids (ERFs). In these systems, polarizable NPs align and reorient along the direction of an applied electric field [2–4], enabling dynamic control over macroscopic properties. ERFs, in particular, consist of suspensions of polarizable particles in an insulating medium and display significant and tunable changes in rheological behavior in the presence of an electric field. These include variations in viscosity, yield stress, and viscoelastic moduli, which make

ERFs promising candidates for applications that demand fast, reversible, and externally controlled mechanical responses [5]. The phenomenon whereby non-conducting particles suspended in a fluid become polarized under an external electric field has its roots in the classical predictions of Clausius [6] and Mossotti [7]. When the dielectric constant of the particles differs from that of the surrounding medium, an electric field induces dipole moments in the particles. As a result, they experience mutual polarization and tend to align both with one another and along the direction of the applied field.

The influence of external electric fields on suspensions of spherical dielectric particles has been extensively studied through experiments [8–12], simulation [13–17] and theory [18–21]. However, such particles typically exhibit lower electrorheological (ER) performance than anisotropic ones, such as rods, tubes, or fibrous particles [22]. This disparity is mainly attributed to the higher length-to-diameter (L/σ) ratio of anisotropic particles, which promotes stronger alignment and interaction under an applied field. Particles with larger L/σ ratios tend to form more stable field-induced structures due to their increased specific surface area and enhanced interparticle friction during reorientation. Although experimental methods for synthesizing anisotropic particles, even those exhibiting especially complex geometries, have advanced considerably, most studies on ERFs have continued to focus primarily on suspensions of nanospheres, with comparatively limited exploration of alternative shapes, including rod-like [23–25], plate-like [26–28] or cubic [29–

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34] particles. Rod-shaped particles, in particular, have shown superior ER activity and mechanical robustness compared to spherical ones, benefiting from the combined effects of their geometry and dielectric properties [22, 35]. These geometric features contribute to improved mechanical stability and a more pronounced ER response.

Molecular simulations of hard and soft rod-like particles have been extensively pursued over the past three decades, addressing a wide range of phenomena in both isotropic and structured phases, including crystalline and liquid-crystalline states. These investigations have provided valuable insights into phase behavior [36–43], dynamics [44–46], and microrheological properties [47, 48], all of which have also been explored in the presence of external fields [49–52]. Understanding the structural and dynamical changes induced by such fields is particularly important in the context of responsive systems, whose macroscopic properties are not only tunable but also inherently time-dependent. A key concept in this framework is the *response time*, namely the characteristic timescale over which a system adjusts from one state to another following the onset or removal of a stimulus. This transition is typically accompanied by a measurable change in physical behavior. Quantifying response times is essential, as the practical utility of responsive materials often depends on their ability to react promptly, particularly so in applications such as adaptive vibration damping or active surface control, where delays can compromise performance.

In this work, we focus on the characterization of response times in systems composed of soft, polarizable colloidal rods initially in isotropic phases where they are randomly oriented. Upon application of a continuous electric field, the particles align along the field direction, inducing a transition to a nematic-like ordered state. To accurately capture the interplay between thermal fluctuations and external forces driving this process, we employ Langevin dynamics simulations. By systematically varying the field intensity, we investigate its impact on the dynamics of this alignment and the associated response times. Furthermore, we assess how these timescales depend on temperature and the magnitude of the induced dipole moments, providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors governing the speed of response in such anisotropic responsive systems. Instead of assuming a fixed intrinsic polarizability, we vary the induced charge and field strength independently with constant charge separation, treating the effective dipole moment as a key variable to generalize the interpretation beyond specific materials.

II. MODEL

To explore the phase behavior and response dynamics of an ERF composed of rod-like colloidal particles subjected to a continuous electric field, we adopt a coarse-grained model based on chains of partially overlapping

spherical beads. Following our earlier work [53], each rod is constructed from eight aligned beads of diameter σ , evenly spaced along the particle’s main axis to achieve an aspect ratio of $L/\sigma = 5$, where L denotes the total length of the rod (see Fig. 1). While increasing the number of constituent beads would yield a more faithful geometric representation of a spherocylinder, the choice of eight beads strikes a practical balance between computational tractability and morphological accuracy. Given the length of the NRs, maintaining their rigidity using commonly employed harmonic bonds is inefficient and prone to numerical instability, even when large spring constants are used. To overcome this, we employ virtual sites that constrain the constituent beads to fixed positions, effectively ensuring structural rigidity without resorting to excessively strong bonding interactions. The total mass of each rod, M , is distributed across two non-interacting mass sites, $M_1 = M_2 = M/2$, placed symmetrically along the rod axis at a fixed distance from the center of mass. This setup preserves both translational invariance and the correct moment of inertia for a uniformly distributed mass. Further details on the placement of the mass sites and the calculation of the effective particle volume are available in our previous work [53]. In the absence of an external electric field, the NRs are treated as electrically neutral, and their intermolecular interactions are modeled as purely dispersive. Specifically, non-bonded interactions between beads belonging to different rods are described by a Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential:

$$U_{ij} = 4\epsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right] \quad (1)$$

where r_{ij} is the distance between beads i and j , and ϵ sets the interaction strength and defines the system’s energy unit. The characteristic time unit is defined as $\tau = \sigma\sqrt{m/\epsilon}$, where $m = M/8$ is the mass of a single bead. The potential is truncated at a cutoff radius of $r_c = 2.4\sigma$, with long-range corrections applied to account for interactions beyond this distance. Considering the rod length $L = 5\sigma$ and the arrangement of 8 beads, the inter-bead spacing is approximately 0.57σ . This configuration yields a particle volume $V_{\text{rod}} \simeq 3.323\sigma^3$ and a mass site separation of about 2.62σ . We notice that this volume underestimates that of a corresponding spherocylinder by roughly 9%.

When an external electric field is applied, the rods become polarized as their electron clouds distort along the particle’s main axis, inducing a dipole moment. This is modeled by assigning two opposite charges, $\pm q$, at the centers of the terminal beads, resulting in a dipole moment of magnitude $\vec{\mu} = q\vec{d}$, where $\|\vec{d}\| = 4\sigma$ denotes the separation distance, and q is varied from 0 to $1e$. Importantly, instead of fixing the intrinsic polarizability associated with a given material, we vary the induced charge magnitude and the applied field strength independently, maintaining a constant charge separation. This approach

enables us to treat the effective dipole moment as a key variable, allowing for a more general interpretation of the observed behavior. It also accounts for potential nonlinearities at high field intensities and avoids limiting the analysis to any particular material system. We note that double-charge models based on the Clausius–Mossotti approximation have also been proposed [50]. While such approaches offer a more explicit treatment of polarizability, they rely on mean-field assumptions that neglect the local electric fields generated by neighboring particles, and thus introduce limitations comparable to those of our effective dipole model, particularly in dense systems. Under these conditions, the total particle interactions are described as the sum of LJ potential, the rod-field interaction,

$$U_{\text{field}} = -\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{E}, \quad (2)$$

and the following Coulombic potential

$$U_{\text{el}}(r_{ij}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \sum_{i,j} \frac{q_i q_j}{r_{ij}}, \quad (3)$$

where the sum runs over all charges q_i belonging to different molecules, r_{ij} is the separation between charge sites i and j , and ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity.

FIG. 1. Geometric representation of the rod-like particle model: **Top:** Ideal spherocylinder characterized by diameter σ , length L , and total mass M . **Middle:** Approximate model consisting of equally spaced, overlapping spherical beads aligned along the main axis. The total mass is distributed into two mass sites positioned to preserve the spherocylinder’s moment of inertia. **Bottom:** Polarized rod model with positive and negative charges, q^+ and q^- , located at the centers of the terminal beads.

III. SIMULATION METHODOLOGY

As a first step toward understanding how the physical properties of an ERF composed of polarizable rod-like

particles vary under an external electric field, we established the phase diagram of the proposed model system. To this end, we performed Langevin dynamics simulations in both the NVT and NPT ensembles using the GROMACS software package [54]. The equations of motion were integrated with the leap-frog stochastic dynamics algorithm, which serves as both integrator and thermostat, enabling efficient temperature control. The integration time step and inverse friction coefficient were set to approximately $3.8 \times 10^{-4}\tau$ and $3.8 \times 10^{-1}\tau$, respectively. Pressure was maintained constant via the Parrinello–Rahman barostat [55], employing a relaxation time of $\sim 3.6 \times 10^{-1}\tau$. The rod internal geometry was maintained using the LINCS algorithm [56]. To investigate the phase behavior, simulations were initialized with 1250 rods randomly placed within a cubic box of side length approximately 22σ , under periodic boundary conditions in all directions. The phase space was explored up to reduced pressures $P^* \equiv P\sigma^3/kT = 5$ and temperatures $T^* \equiv k_B T/\epsilon = 8$, with k_B the Boltzmann’s constant. For each thermodynamic state point, an initial equilibration phase was conducted until both pressure and temperature stabilized. Production runs were then carried out for $t/\tau \simeq 9.4 \times 10^3$, saving system configurations approximately every 3.8τ . All thermodynamic and structural properties were computed from the equilibrated portion of the trajectory, identified from the stability of the total energy profile.

In order to distinguish between the different phases (isotropic, nematic, smectic, crystalline solid), we evaluated the orientational ordering of the system using the nematic order parameter S_2 , defined as the largest eigenvalue of the ordering tensor:

$$Q_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i=1}^N (3\hat{u}_{i\alpha}\hat{u}_{i\beta} - \delta_{\alpha\beta}) \quad (4)$$

where \hat{u}_i is the unit vector along the axis of the i -th rod, $\delta_{\alpha\beta}$ is the Kronecker delta, and the indices $\alpha, \beta \in \{x, y, z\}$. The summation runs over all N rods in the system. The parameter S_2 ranges from values close to zero in the isotropic phase to values approaching unity in highly aligned phases. While S_2 quantifies the global orientational order, additional structural information was obtained by analyzing the spatial distribution of neighboring rods through the radial, parallel, and perpendicular pair distribution functions. These are defined as

$$g(\mathbf{d}) = \frac{N_p}{\rho N N_c V(\mathbf{d})}, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{d} = \{\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_{\parallel}, \mathbf{r}_{\perp}\}$, with \mathbf{r} the center-to-center distance vector between two rods, and \mathbf{r}_{\parallel} and \mathbf{r}_{\perp} its projections along and perpendicular to the nematic director $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$, respectively. Here, N_p is the number of particle pairs found within the volume element $V(\mathbf{d})$, ρ is the number density, N is the total number of particles, and N_c the number of sampled configurations. Once the thermodynamic conditions corresponding to a stable isotropic

phase were identified, a uniform electric field was applied along the z -axis to investigate the system's response to the external stimulus. To enhance statistical reliability, the final equilibrated configuration at a given pressure and temperature was replicated four times along the z -direction, while maintaining the same average density. A short NVT equilibration run was then performed to ensure isotropic conditions prior to the application of the field.

A continuous electric field of reduced magnitude $E^* = \mu E/k_B T$, ranging from 0 to 1000, was applied along the z -axis, parallel to the long axis of the simulation box. This field induces a dipolar polarization in the rod-like particles, modeled by assigning opposite charges $\pm q$ at the centers of the outermost beads. The reduced charge magnitude $q^* \equiv q/e$ was varied from 0 to 1. By maintaining a fixed charge separation while independently adjusting the charge magnitude and field strength, the effective dipole moment is treated as a tunable parameter, allowing us to investigate a broad spectrum of dipolar interactions beyond those constrained by fixed material polarizabilities. Although values smaller than the elementary charge may initially appear unphysical, this practice is well established in coarse-grained simulations, where q serves as an effective interaction parameter and may also be viewed as a statistical average of partial charge accumulation at the rod ends that characterizes tunneling effects in conducting materials separated by a potential barrier. Consequently, it enables continuous adjustment of the dipolar coupling strength without modifying the particle geometry or imposing discrete charge quantization. Upon deactivation of the electric field, the rods naturally return to a neutral state. Electrostatic interactions were computed using the Coulomb potential between charged sites belonging to different rods only. Long-range electrostatics were handled using the Particle Mesh Ewald (PME) method [57].

The structural and dynamic response of the system to the applied electric field was investigated through NVT simulations comprising 10 alternating cycles of field activation and deactivation. To characterize potential metastable states, we measured the nematic order parameter, pair distribution functions, and diffusion coefficient across various field strengths and charge magnitudes, under different pressure and temperature conditions. The response times τ^{on} and τ^{off} were defined as the times required for the system to reach 95% of the corresponding equilibrium values of the nematic order parameter after the field is switched on or off, denoted as $\langle S_2^{\text{on}} \rangle$ and $\langle S_2^{\text{off}} \rangle$, respectively. Specifically, τ^{on} is the time at which $S_2 = 0.95 \times \langle S_2^{\text{on}} \rangle$ is reached following field application, while τ^{off} is defined by the condition $S_2 = 1 - 0.95 \times \langle S_2^{\text{off}} \rangle$ after the field is removed.

IV. RESULTS

This study is structured in two main parts. First, we investigated the phase behavior of a system of neutral rod-like particles with an aspect ratio of $L/\sigma = 5$ across a wide range of temperatures and pressures, with the goal of identifying the thermodynamic conditions under which the isotropic phase is stable. It is important to note that for neutral rods, aligned structures are observed even at zero applied field ($E = 0$), highlighting that packing effects alone can induce alignment without any external electric field. Once these conditions were established, we applied a constant electric field of varying strength to the system of polarizable rods in order to characterize both the resulting disorder-order phase transition and the timescales associated with the system's response to the external stimulus.

A. Phase Diagram of Neutral Rods

FIG. 2. P^* vs T^* phase diagram for a system of rods with aspect ratio $L/\sigma = 5$. The light blue region corresponds to structured phase (nematic, smectic, or crystalline), while light green region represents the liquid (isotropic) phase. Representative snapshots of typical configurations are shown for each region.

The phase diagram of similar rigid bead-necklace prolate particles has been previously investigated by Tian and Smith [58], who considered rods with an aspect ratio of 7 interacting *via* the LJ potential. They identified an isotropic phase at packing fractions $\eta < 0.420$, a nematic phase in the intermediate range $0.420 < \eta < 0.514$, and smectic A and crystalline phases at higher densities. We first analyze the phase behavior of a system composed of neutral rod-like particles with aspect ratio $L/\sigma = 5$, interacting exclusively via the LJ potential, as described in Section II. To this end, NPT simulations were carried out for 1250 uncharged rods over a range of reduced pressures $0 < P^* < 5$ and temperatures $0 < T^* < 8$. Rods were initially placed at random positions within the simulation

box, and the system was equilibrated under the desired thermodynamic conditions. Production runs were then performed for a total simulation time of $t/\tau \simeq 9.4 \times 10^3$, during which the density, nematic order parameter, and pair distribution functions were computed to characterize the emerging phases. As shown in Fig. 2, the phase diagram reveals two predominant regions: a low-density isotropic (fluid-like) phase and a high-density structured phase. In this work, our interest is specifically restricted to the transition between disordered and ordered states induced by an external electric field. Therefore, we focus solely on the isotropic regime, and a detailed characterization of the structured region in equilibrium is not pursued. The isotropic phase emerges at temperatures above $T^* \approx 5$, with the transition temperature increasing with pressure. This region is characterized by a low orientational order parameter ($S_2 \lesssim 0.1$), moderate packing fraction ($\eta \lesssim 0.5$), and relatively high mobility, as indicated by diffusion coefficients $D^* = D\tau/\sigma^2 \gtrsim 0.01$. In contrast, the structured phase exhibits pronounced orientational order ($S_2 \gtrsim 0.4$), higher density ($\eta \gtrsim 0.5$), and significantly reduced diffusion ($D^* \ll 0.01$), indicating the emergence of positional and orientational correlations characteristic of ordered phases. Representative snapshots of the system at $(P^*, T^*) = (1, 5)$ and $(1, 6)$ are shown in Fig. 2, illustrating the distinct structural features of each phase.

Further structural insight is provided by the analysis of the pair distribution functions (PDFs) defined in Eq. (5). Figure 3 displays the radial distribution $g(r)$, along with its parallel $g_{\parallel}(r_{\parallel})$ and perpendicular $g_{\perp}(r_{\perp})$ components relative to the nematic director. These functions are calculated by considering the center-of-mass distance vector \mathbf{r} between each pair of rods and projecting it onto directions parallel and perpendicular to the director. For the representative isotropic state at $(P^*, T^*) = (1, 6)$ (blue curves), both $g(r)$ and $g_{\perp}(r_{\perp})$ exhibit a pronounced peak near $r^* \equiv r/\sigma \approx 1.1$, with the first coordination shell extending up to $r^* \approx 3$. Beyond this range, the functions rapidly decay to unity, as expected for a disordered, low-density fluid. In contrast, the parallel component $g_{\parallel}(r_{\parallel})$ remains flat across all distances, confirming the absence of positional correlations or layering along the nematic director—consistent with a fully isotropic arrangement. In contrast, at $(P^*, T^*) = (1, 5)$, the system displays a markedly different behavior, indicative of structural ordering in both the radial and perpendicular directions. As shown by the red curves in Fig. 3, the pair distribution functions exhibit a sequence of well-defined peaks and troughs, reflecting the presence of short- and medium-range positional order. In particular, the parallel distribution function $g_{\parallel}(r_{\parallel})$ reveals a pronounced layered structure, with a periodicity of approximately 5.5σ , slightly exceeding the rod length—consistent with smectic-like organization.

FIG. 3. Radial (top), perpendicular (middle), and parallel (bottom) pair distribution functions of a structured phase (red line) and an isotropic phase (blue line) at $(P^*, T^*) = (1, 5)$ and $(1, 6)$, respectively. The corresponding nematic order parameters are $S_2 = 0.72$ for the structured phase and $S_2 = 0.04$ for the isotropic phase. Here $r^* = r/\sigma$ is the reduced distance.

B. Effect of an Electric Field on Polarizable Rods

Having established the conditions for the isotropic phase, we proceeded to investigate the response of polarizable rods to an external electric field. Systems with rod charges $q^* = \pm 0.1, \pm 0.3, \text{ and } \pm 0.5$ were studied at a fixed pressure $P^* = 1$ and temperatures $T^* = 6, 7, \text{ and } 8$. To enhance statistical accuracy and reduce finite-size effects, the final equilibrated configuration under each set of conditions was replicated fourfold along the z -axis, yielding systems of 5000 rods. A short equilibration run followed each replication to ensure structural and thermodynamic consistency before applying the electric field. *NVT* simulations were conducted using cyclic protocols where a constant electric field E^* , ranging from 0 to 1000, was periodically switched on and off along the z -axis. When the field is applied, we assume that the polarization of the rods, arising from electron cloud distortions along the particle axis, occurs on a timescale much shorter than their mechanical reorientation or translational response. Therefore, rods are considered instantaneously polarized, and the charged rod model, with opposite charges localized at the ends, is employed to capture the resulting dipolar interactions. Upon removal of the field, the charges are assumed to rapidly redistribute along the rod backbone, restoring electrical neutrality and effectively switching back to the neutral rod model. This approach allows us to isolate and investigate the rods' structural and dynamic responses to the external field under realistic assumptions about polarization kinetics.

FIG. 4. Equilibrium snapshots of a system of 5000 rods with $q^* = \pm 0.5$ at $P^* = 1$ and $T^* = 7$. The top panel shows the configuration with the electric field switched off ($E^* = 0$), while the bottom panel corresponds to the field switched on ($E^* = 7$) along the z -direction.

Fig. 4 displays two representative configurations of the system with the electric field switched off and on, respectively. Upon application of the field, the rods exhibit strong alignment along the field direction (the z -axis), resulting in a highly ordered nematic state. Under the conditions indicated in the figure, the system reaches a nematic order parameter of $S_2 = 0.8$. The dynamical re-

sponse to repeated switching of the electric field is illustrated in Fig. 5, where the evolution of S_2 is tracked over several on/off cycles. When the field is turned on, the system rapidly responds, with S_2 rising sharply and stabilizing at a characteristic value determined by the field strength and system parameters. At low field strengths (e.g., $E^* = 1.8$), thermal fluctuations dominate over dipolar interactions, resulting in weak alignment. In this regime, the order parameter remains relatively low, with $S_2 \approx 0.3$ for rods bearing charges $q^* = \pm 0.5$ at $P^* = 1$ and $T^* = 7$. As the field strength increases, the influence of the electric torque on the polarized rods grows, progressively suppressing rotational motion. At high field intensities, such as $E^* = 69.6$, the system approaches nearly perfect alignment, with the order parameter reaching $S_2 \approx 0.97$.

FIG. 5. Time evolution of the nematic order parameter S_2 for a system of 5000 rods with charge $q^* = \pm 0.5$, at $P^* = 1$ and $T^* = 7$, subjected to periodic cycles of a constant electric field applied along the z -axis. Curves correspond to different field strengths: $E^* = 0$ (black), 1.8 (red), 3.5 (green), 7.0 (blue), 13.9 (brown), and 69.6 (orange). The degree of alignment increases with field strength, as reflected in the rise of S_2 during the active phase of each cycle.

To further assess the dynamical response of the system to external electric fields, we analyzed the short-time evolution of the nematic order parameter S_2 immediately following the switching on and off of the field. The results, shown in Fig. 6 for the first on/off cycle, reveal a clear asymmetry between the ordering and disordering processes. Upon field application, S_2 rises rapidly as the rods align along the field direction. In contrast, when the field is removed, the loss of orientational order proceeds more gradually, particularly at high field strengths. Interestingly, for weaker fields, this trend is reversed: the disordering kinetics is faster than the ordering, suggesting a subtle interplay between dipolar coupling and thermal fluctuations in the system's relaxation behavior. Both processes are well described by exponential functions of the form $S_2^{\text{on}}(t) \propto 1 - \exp[-b(t/t_0)^c]$ (switching on) and $S_2^{\text{off}}(t) \propto \exp[-b(t/t_0)^c]$ (switching off), where

t_0 is a characteristic relaxation time, which is inversely proportional to the particle average rotational diffusion coefficient [59], while b and c are fitting parameters. This exponential behavior is reminiscent of the optical Kerr effect, wherein an initially isotropic medium develops birefringence upon application of an external electric field. According to Kerr's law, the induced birefringence Δn increases with time and, in the case of dilute suspensions of particles without intrinsic dipole moments and under weak electric fields, scales with the square of the field strength: $\Delta n(t) = KE^2 [1 - \exp(-(t/\tau_K)^\alpha)]$. Here, K is the Kerr constant, τ_K is a characteristic optical relaxation time, and α is an empirical exponent [60–62]. When the field is switched off, the birefringence decays in a manner closely linked to the distribution of the particles' rotational diffusion coefficients. This decay generally follows a similar exponential function, although alternative forms, based on the Watson-Jennings and multi-exponential methods, have also been proposed [59]. Since birefringence originates from orientational anisotropy, it is directly proportional to the nematic order parameter $S_2(t)$, particularly in the weak-alignment regime. Therefore, the exponential form used to fit our simulation data reflects a kinetic process closely related to that underlying Kerr birefringence buildup. This analogy underscores the physical connection between microscopic orientational ordering and macroscopic optical responses, with the fitting parameters t_0 and c capturing the influence of dipolar interactions and thermal fluctuations on the system's relaxation dynamics.

FIG. 6. Short-time evolution of the nematic order parameter S_2 during the initial stages of field application (left) and removal (right) for polarizable rods under a constant electric field along the z -axis. Symbols indicate different field strengths: $E^* = 1.8$ (\circ), $E^* = 3.5$ (\square), $E^* = 7.0$ (\diamond), $E^* = 13.9$ (\triangle), $E^* = 69.6$ (\triangleright). Solid lines represent exponential fits of the form $S_2(t) \propto 1 - \exp[-b(t/t_0)^c]$ (left) and $S_2(t) \propto \exp[-b(t/t_0)^c]$ (right), where t_0 is a characteristic relaxation time, and b and c are fitting parameters.

To investigate the influence of thermal energy on field-

induced ordering, we examined the nematic response at three different temperatures: $T^* = 6, 7,$ and 8 . For each case, the average nematic order parameter S_2 was computed over 10 complete cycles of field switching. The results, shown in the top panel of Fig. 7, display the equilibrium values of S_2 as a function of the applied electric field strength E^* for a system of 5000 rods with charge $q^* = \pm 0.5$ at fixed pressure $P^* = 1$. At low field strengths ($E^* < 2$), rod alignment remains weak, and the system retains its isotropic character. Beyond this threshold, the order parameter increases markedly with field strength, indicating progressive alignment along the field direction. Notably, at high fields ($E^* > 100$), the system reaches nearly perfect nematic order irrespective of temperature. However, at intermediate field strengths, thermal fluctuations play a more prominent role, and higher temperatures lead to reduced alignment, as evidenced by the lower values of $\langle S_2^{\text{on}} \rangle$. In this regime, the system approaches the behavior expected for an ideal ensemble of non-interacting dipoles, as represented by the dashed reference curve in the figure. These results highlight the competition between thermal agitation and field-induced orientational ordering in determining the system's macroscopic response. When the field is switched off, the average order parameter S_2^{off} relaxes to the value observed during the pre-equilibration stage, as shown in the inset of Fig. 7. The slight differences between datasets reflect the temperature-dependent equilibrium values. Based on this behavior and following the definition of the response times introduced in the previous section, we computed the average switching times τ^{on} and τ^{off} for each condition. The bottom panel of Fig. 7 shows the dependence of the response times τ^{on} and τ^{off} (inset) on the applied electric field. As observed, τ^{on} decreases with both increasing temperature and field strength. At very high field values, the switching-on time approaches a constant value, $\tau^{\text{on}}_\infty \approx 0.96$. In contrast, τ^{off} increases with field strength, reflecting the fact that a higher degree of alignment requires more time for the system to relax back to a disordered state once the field is removed. However, beyond a certain threshold, both S_2 and τ^{off} saturate, becoming independent of further increases in field intensity. This insensitivity of τ^{off} to the field is primarily due to the relaxation being fundamentally dominated by the rotational diffusion of the rods. The residual dependence of τ^{off} on the field strength can be attributed to the system's non-dilute nature, which imposes constraints on particle motion that are more pronounced when starting from a higher initial alignment at larger E^* .

Finally, we examine the effect of varying dipole charges on the nematic order parameter S_2 and the response times τ^{on} and τ^{off} at fixed pressure $P^* = 1$ and temperature $T^* = 6$. As shown in Fig. 8, when the electric field is applied, both the order parameter S_2^{on} and the response time τ^{on} exhibit a universal trend that is largely independent of the specific dipole charge assigned to the rods. At high field strengths, the system approaches the

FIG. 7. Average nematic order parameter and corresponding response times as a function of electric field strength for a system of 5000 rods at pressure $P^* = 1$ and temperatures $T^* = 6, 7$, and 8 . Ten cycles of a constant electric field being switched on and off (illustrated in the inset) were applied. Upon field application, the rods acquire a charge $q^* = \pm 0.5$, whereas they become neutral ($q^* = 0$) when the field is removed. The dashed curve represents the equilibrium S_2 value for an ideal dipolar system (see text for details), while the solid lines are fits to the response time data. Error bars are smaller than the symbol size unless otherwise specified.

behavior of an ideal dipolar fluid, and the response time asymptotically approaches $\tau_\infty^{\text{on}} \approx 0.96$. When the field is switched off, S_2^{off} returns to the equilibrium value corresponding to $P^* = 1$ and $T^* = 6$, as expected. The response time τ^{off} follows a general increasing trend with electric field strength and ultimately reaches a plateau at approximately $\tau_\infty^{\text{off}} \approx 65$ under these conditions.

To rationalize the universal behavior observed at high field strengths, we now present an analytical treatment of the equilibrium order parameter for a dilute ideal gas of dipolar rods under an external electric field. Consider a system of N identical dipolar rods in a volume V , in the highly dilute limit such that interparticle interactions are negligible. In this regime, the system behaves as a

FIG. 8. Average nematic order parameter and corresponding response times as a function of electric field strength for a system of 5000 rods at $P^* = 1$, $T^* = 6$ and charges $q^* = \pm 0.1, \pm 0.3$ and ± 0.5 . Ten cycles of a constant electric field being switched on and off (illustrated in the inset) were applied. Upon field application, the rods acquire a charge $q^* = \pm 0.5$, whereas they become neutral ($q^* = 0$) when the field is removed. The dashed curve represents the equilibrium S_2 value for an ideal dipolar system (see text for details), while the solid lines are fits to the response time data. Error bars are smaller than the symbol size unless otherwise specified.

classical ideal gas. Upon application of an external field, the interaction energy of a single dipole is given by

$$\varepsilon = -\mu E \cos \theta, \quad (6)$$

where θ denotes the angle between the dipole axis and the field. The canonical partition function of the system is $Z = (Z_1)^N / N!$, where Z_1 is the single-particle partition function. For a classical particle with center-of-mass coordinates x, y, z and orientation specified by the Euler

angles ϕ, θ, ψ , the Hamiltonian reads

$$H_1 = \frac{p_x^2}{2M} + \frac{p_y^2}{2M} + \frac{p_z^2}{2M} + \frac{(p_\phi - p_\psi \cos \theta)^2}{2I_1 \sin^2 \theta} + \frac{p_\theta^2}{2I_1} + \frac{p_\psi^2}{2I_3} - \mu E \cos \theta, \quad (7)$$

where I_1 and I_3 are the principal moments of inertia of the rod. Integrating over all phase-space variables yields the single-particle partition function:

$$Z_1 = \frac{1}{h^6} \int e^{-H_1/kT} d\mathbf{q} d\mathbf{p} = \frac{8\pi^2 V}{h^6} (2\pi kT)^3 M^{3/2} I_1 I_3^{1/2} \cdot \frac{\sinh(E^*)}{E^*} \quad (8)$$

where the dimensionless parameter $E^* = \mu E/kT$ quantifies the relative strength of field-induced alignment versus thermal agitation. The corresponding equilibrium order parameter, $\langle S(E^*) \rangle = \langle P_2(\cos \theta) \rangle$, reads

$$\langle S(E^*) \rangle = \frac{1}{h^6 Z_1} \int e^{-\beta H_1} P_2(\cos \theta) d\mathbf{q} d\mathbf{p} = 1 - \frac{3 \coth(E^*)}{E^*} + \frac{3}{(E^*)^2}, \quad (9)$$

which is plotted as the dashed line in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. This function satisfies the expected limiting behavior: $\langle S(0) \rangle = 0$ (isotropic state), monotonic increase with E^* , and $\lim_{E^* \rightarrow \infty} \langle S \rangle = 1$, corresponding to perfect alignment. The lack of universal scaling in the simulation data stems from the system's inherent non-ideality. Unlike an ideal gas, the simulated dipolar rods interact via excluded volume and attractive LJ forces, breaking the ideal scaling with E^* . These interactions induce many-body effects, including spontaneous alignment at finite density and zero field, leading to a finite baseline order parameter and increased temperature sensitivity. Such collective phenomena account for the deviations from ideal behavior and preclude collapse onto a single master curve.

V. CONCLUSION

We have investigated the orientational response of dipolar rod-like particles to an external electric field by combining Langevin dynamics simulations with analytical theory. As a first step, we characterized the phase behavior of our bead-necklace model in the absence of external fields to identify the thermodynamic conditions under which isotropic and structurally ordered phases emerge. This preliminary mapping allowed us to select state points within the stability region of the isotropic phase, ensuring that field-induced alignment could be unambiguously distinguished from spontaneous ordering due to interparticle interactions. Using cyclic field-switching protocols, we then quantified the system's non-equilibrium response by measuring the nematic order parameter and the corresponding response times during the

field-on and field-off periods. Our model does not assume a fixed intrinsic polarizability characteristic of a specific material. Instead, by varying the charge magnitude and electric field independently while keeping the charge separation constant, we treat the effective dipole moment as a tunable parameter. This allows us to explore a broader response landscape and to account for potential nonlinearities in the polarization response at high field strengths. We observe a rich interplay between dipolar coupling, thermal fluctuations, and interparticle interactions. At sufficiently strong fields, the system exhibits a universal alignment response, largely independent of the specific dipole moment, characterized by a plateau in the order parameter and a saturation of the alignment time. To rationalize this high-field behavior, we developed an analytical treatment based on a classical ideal gas of dipolar rods. In the dilute limit, we derived a closed-form expression for the equilibrium order parameter as a function of the dimensionless field strength $E^* = \mu E/kT$. This model accurately reproduces the observed universal trend at high fields, predicting full alignment in the limit $E^* \rightarrow \infty$ and isotropic behavior at zero field. The analytical expression serves as a useful benchmark for interpreting simulation results and for exploring the response in regimes not easily accessible computationally. However, our simulations also highlight clear deviations from ideal-gas behavior. At finite densities, dipolar rods interact through excluded volume and LJ interactions, giving rise to spontaneous orientational correlations even in the absence of external fields. These interactions enhance the temperature dependence of the alignment response and lead to a nonzero order parameter at zero field, thus precluding a full collapse of simulation data onto a universal master curve. In summary, our study provides a detailed particle-level understanding of field-induced ordering in dipolar fluids. It establishes connections between idealized analytical predictions and the complex behavior observed in simulations, offering both theoretical insight and practical guidance for the design of responsive anisotropic materials under external stimuli.

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